

Mathematical Logic and Physical Mechanism Behind the Lorentz Transformation and Special Relativity

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Abstract: In different inertial reference frames, people have different perceptions of time and distance. When it is necessary to convert the spacetime coordinates between two inertial reference frames, subtle changes occur in the coordinates of time and space. These changes are precisely described by the Lorentz transformation formula. The Lorentz transformation plays a crucial role in physics, and the set of equations for the transformation of spacetime coordinates in special relativity also reveals the relativity and unity of spacetime. However, we should also note that there are indeed clear differences in mathematical form between the Lorentz transformation and special relativity. This article aims to provide a detailed explanation of the Lorentz transformation and special relativity, thoroughly analyze the differences and commonalities between them, and reveal the mathematical logic and physical mechanisms behind the Lorentz transformation and special relativity.

Keywords: Lorentz transformation; Special relativity; Galilean transformation; Time dilation; MMX; Fitzgerald Contraction

1. Introduction

In the 19th century, scientists widely believed in the existence of a substance called the luminiferous ether, through which light was thought to propagate. The Michelson-Morley experiment (MMX)[1], shown in Figure 1, was a highly significant experiment conducted in 1887 by American physicists Albert Michelson and Edward Morley. Its purpose was to explore the existence of the ether and the manner in which light propagated. The experiment involved splitting a beam of light along two perpendicular paths and recombining them to observe interference patterns. However, the results of the experiment showed that the speed of light was independent of the Earth's motion, indicating that the speed of light on the Earth's surface is constant and unaffected by the Earth's motion or the presence of the ether.

Figure 1: Michelson-Morley Experiment

MMX has been repeated multiple times with increasing sensitivity. This includes experiments conducted from 1902 to 1905, as well as a series of experiments in the 1920s. In a recent development in 2009, an optical resonator experiment confirmed the absence of any "ether wind" at the level of 10⁻¹⁷. The results of MMX demonstrated that the "ether wind" does not exist, thereby refuting theories of an absolute stationary ether or a partially dragged ether. The only plausible explanation for MMX is if the ether is completely dragged by the Earth; however, this explanation encounters difficulties in explaining phenomena such as stellar aberration.[2]

When explaining the MMX, Lorentz proposed the concept of ether contraction to account for the invariance of the speed of light. He suggested that even if the ether existed, it would not affect the measurement of the speed of light due to a phenomenon called "Fitzgerald contraction." [3] According to this idea, as the ether serves as the medium for light propagation, its motion influences the intermolecular forces in the instrument, causing a reduction in the distance between molecules, resulting in ether compression. This compression leads to a shorter path for light traveling in the direction of the ether wind, allowing it to arrive at the observation point simultaneously with light traveling perpendicular to the ether wind. In simpler terms, if you want to measure a length that has undergone compression, you need to use a ruler. However, the ruler itself is also compressed, and the time coordinates must be modified ("local time"). Therefore, this compression effect cannot be measured directly. Lorentz's explanation reconciled the contradiction between the constancy of the speed of light and the existence of the ether by

introducing the idea of ether compression, providing a new perspective for the physics community at the time.

However, it is important to note that the existence of the ether has not been directly observed, and the hypothesis of ether contraction also faces theoretical difficulties. Nevertheless, the Lorentz transformation[4], which provides the basic relationship for the transformation of physical events in space and time between different inertial frames, has had a profound impact on the development of modern physics.

2. Derivation of the Lorentz Transformation

Lorentz attempted to explain the invariance of the speed of light by invoking ether contraction, which was a classical physics perspective. Although the notion of ether contraction has been abandoned, it is still true that in two different inertial reference frames, S and S' , people have different perceptions of time and distance. Therefore, even without the existence of the ether, we can make different measurements of physical events in each inertial reference frame. The Lorentz transformation is a mathematically rigorous spacetime coordinate transformation based on the premise of the constancy of the speed of light in any inertial reference frame. Next, we will derive the Lorentz transformation equations by considering the reference frames S and S' .

In Figure 1, let's consider two inertial coordinate systems, S and S' . The origin O' of the S' moves with a velocity v along the positive direction of the X -axis relative to the origin O of the S . The spacetime coordinates of an arbitrary event in the S and S' are (x, y, z, t) and (x', y', z', t') , respectively. Here, t and t' represent the moments in time for the S and S' , respectively. The measured speed of light in both S and S' is constant and denoted as c . Now, let's imagine that a beam of light is emitted from the coincident origins O (O') along the positive x -axis. The coordinates of the wavefront when it reaches point P , as observed in the S and S' systems, are (X, Y, Z, T) and (X', Y', Z', T') , respectively.

Figure 2: Inertial Reference Frame Model in the Lorentz Transformation

When the two inertial coordinate systems coincide, the coordinate origin is set at ($x = x' = 0$), and the time measurement starts. When the light reaches point P, the elapsed time for S' is T' , and the distance S' has moved forward is vT' . We have:

$$OX = vT' + X', \quad (1)$$

for S, the elapsed time is T, and the distance S' has moved forward is vT . We have:

$$O'X' = X - vT \quad (2)$$

We hypothesize the existence of a γ (which could be a constant or a function) that can mathematically make the following equation hold true:

$$X = \gamma(X' + vT'), \quad (3)$$

$$X' = \gamma(X - vT). \quad (4)$$

There is no relative velocity between y and y' , z and z' , so their coordinates are the same. Therefore, we only need to analyze the x -axis. Substituting equation (2) into equation (1), we can solve for T' .

$$T' = \gamma T + (1 - \gamma^2)X / \gamma v. \quad (5)$$

Since the measured speed of light is constant and equal to c in both S and S', we have:

$$X = cT, \quad (6)$$

$$X' = cT'. \quad (7)$$

Multiplying equations (3) and (4), we obtain:

$$XX' = \gamma^2 (XX' - X'vT + XvT' - v^2TT'), \quad (8)$$

substituting equations (6) and (7) into equation (8), we obtain:

$$cTcT' = \gamma^2(cTcT' - cT'vT + cTvT' - v^2TT') = \gamma^2(cTcT' - v^2TT') , \quad (9)$$

rearranging, we obtain:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2 / c^2}} , \quad (10)$$

This is an equation that is independent of distance coordinates and time coordinates. Therefore, our earlier mathematical hypothesis regarding the existence of a γ that satisfies both equations (3) and (4) simultaneously is valid. γ is the Lorentz factor.

Substituting equation (10) into equations (4) and (5), and replacing T with t, X with x, and X' with x', we obtain the general form of the Lorentz transformation from the S system to the S' system.

$$t' = \gamma(t - vx / c^2) , \quad (11)$$

$$x' = \gamma(x - vt) . \quad (12)$$

The Lorentz transformation from the S' to the S is given by:

$$x = \gamma(x' + vt') , \quad (13)$$

$$t = \gamma(t' + vx' / c^2) . \quad (14)$$

Thus, the Lorentz factor establishes a connection between the time and distance coordinates in the S and S' systems, allowing for the conversion between distance and time coordinates in both systems. The Lorentz transformation is based on the premise that the speed of light is constant, denoted as c, in any inertial reference frame. From equations (1) and (2), we can see that the Lorentz transformation combines the speed of light and the velocity of the reference frame.

Clearly, different reference frames must have their own "local time scale" and "local distance scale" in order to maintain the premise of the constancy of the speed of light, c, in any inertial reference frame. In other words, the essence behind the constancy of the speed of light, c, phenomenon is the difference in the time and distance scales of different reference frames.

From the derivation process, we can see that the Lorentz transformation describes the difference in the calculation of time for the same event in different reference frames. We know that Einstein

derived special relativity based on the Lorentz transformation, but they are so different in mathematical form. This raises the question: Are the times transformed by them consistent with each other?

3. Spatiotemporal Coordinate Transformation Based on Galilean Transformation

If observers in S and S' calculate the time of light propagation in S' using the Galilean transformation as T1 and T2 respectively, and then compare the relationship between T1 and T2, what would the result be? Following this line of thought, we conducted an analysis.

Figure 3: Inertial Reference Frame Model in Galilean Transformation

As shown in Figure 3, in S, light takes time T to reach point A, resulting in

$$X = cT, \quad (15)$$

Since the speed of light in S' is equal to c, according to the Galilean transformation, observers in the S reference frame would naturally assume that the speed of light in S' would be added to the velocity v of the S' frame. Thus, the relative velocity of light in S' with respect to S is c+v.

Therefore, we obtain:

$$vT_1 + cT_1 = cT, \quad (16)$$

therefore, the time required for the distance L in Figure 3 is:

$$T_1 = cT / (c + v). \quad (17)$$

Next, we calculate the time required for the distance L from the perspective of an observer in S':

$$T_2 = L / c = (X - vT) / c = (c - v)T / c. \quad (18)$$

From equations (17) and (18), we obtain:

$$T_2 = (c^2 - v^2) / c^2 * T_1 . \quad (19)$$

The above analysis reveals that observer S considers that S' has the same time and distance scale as S. Therefore, S perceives the speed of light in S' relative to S as c+v. Based on the classical Galilean transformations, S calculates T1.

Similarly, observer S' also considers that its own time and distance scale are the same as S. Using the Galilean transformations, S' calculates T2. In other words, under the assumption that S and S' mutually perceive each other's distances and time scales to be consistent with their own, they independently calculate the time it takes for light to travel a distance L. However, in reality, in order to maintain the constancy of c, their time and distance scales must be different. Therefore, Equation (19) represents the result of the dual influence of the inconsistent time and distance scales between S and S'.

We know that speed is defined as distance divided by time. Therefore, redefining the scales of distance and time (localization) can change the numerical value of speed. Let's consider a simple example: if we only redefine the concept of a second, where the new definition of 1 second is equal to the previous 2 seconds, then the speed will become twice its previous value. Now let's analyze how the scales of time and distance determine speed.

In S, assuming Len represents the distance covered by light in Time, we have:

$$c = Len / Time , \quad (20)$$

assuming the localized distance Len' in S' is K times the localized distance Len in S, we have:

$$Len' = Len * K . \quad (21)$$

Therefore, considering that the time scale remains the same, since the distance in S' becomes Len * K, the distance is divided by c, and S' requires K times more time, i.e., Time * K. Then, from $c = Len' / Time'$, in order to keep c unchanged, the distance scale becomes K times, and the time scale also needs to be multiplied by K. Therefore, under the dual influence of time and distance scales, the time in S' is K * K times that of S. Consequently, according to the respective time and distance scales of S and S', we have:

$$Time' = Time * KK . \quad (22)$$

Here's an example: In system A, the time scale is $s = 1$, and the distance scale is 1. In system B, the time scale is $s' = 0.8$, and the distance scale is 0.8.

This means that the ruler in system B has become shorter. In system B, 1 meter is equivalent to only 0.8 meters in system A. Similarly, 1 second in system B is equivalent to only 0.8 seconds in system A.

Now, let's consider a distance L measured in system A. The time it takes for light to travel this distance is $Ta = (L/c)$ s. In system B's perspective, the length of this distance is $L*0.8$, and the time it takes for light to travel is

$$Tb = (L*0.8/c) s' = (Ta*0.8*0.8) s . \quad (23)$$

From equations (19) and (23), we obtain:

$$K^2 = (c^2 - v^2) / c^2 , \quad (24)$$

$$K = \sqrt{(c^2 - v^2) / c^2} . \quad (25)$$

The relationship between K and the Lorentz factor γ is:

$$K = 1/\gamma \quad (26)$$

In equation (18), T_2 represents the time calculated in system S using the distance scale of S, where L is the numerical value of distance given in S's scale. Now we want to switch it to the distance scale of S', measuring it using S' scale. Since the scale of S' is K times that of S, the numerical value of the distance L in S' scale needs to be divided by K . In simpler terms, when the ruler becomes shorter, the numerical values measured by the ruler will become larger. Therefore, we need to replace L with $L' = L/K$. Thus, we can calculate the required time T_2' in the distance scale of S', resulting in:

$$T_2' = L'/c = L/K/c = T_2/K = T(c-v)/K/c , \quad (27)$$

rearranging the equation, we obtain:

$$T_2' = \sqrt{(c^2 - v^2) / c^2} * T_1 . \quad (28)$$

Thus, we have obtained the relationship between the time T' calculated in S' distance scale and the time T_1 calculated in S distance scale. In terms of form, equation (28) is consistent with the time relationship equation in special relativity [5]. Based on the constancy of the speed of light c , we can also derive the distance transformation equations in the respective time scales of S and S'.

$$L' = \sqrt{(c^2 - v^2) / c^2} * L . \quad (29)$$

Under the assumption that S and S' perceive each other's distance and time scales to be consistent with their own, we have derived time and distance equations consistent with special relativity using Galilean transformations. Therefore, we have reason to believe that the mathematical logic behind special relativity operates in a similar manner. Equations (28) and (29) represent the result of the dual influence of the inconsistent time and distance scales between inertial reference frames.

Therefore, the physical mechanism of special relativity is different from the Lorentz transformations. It describes the differences in the calculation of time for the same event within the same reference frame as observed by observers in different reference frames.

4. Differences and Commonalities between Lorentz Transformations and Special Relativity

Now we can answer why the Lorentz transformations and special relativity are mathematically inconsistent. It is because they have different mathematical meanings. The Lorentz transformations describe the differences in time calculations for the same event in different reference frames. Special relativity, on the other hand, describes the differences in time calculations for the same event within the same reference frame as observed by observers in different reference frames.

Both the Lorentz transformations and special relativity reveal a mathematical logic: the differences in time and distance scales between inertial reference frames result in different time calculations. Therefore, by establishing different time and distance scales, we can ensure that the numerical value of velocity for a particular object remains the same in their respective inertial reference frames. Let's consider **an interesting example**.

Consider a train with a long carriage moving in a straight line with a constant speed v on a railway track. When the train passes through position P1, two identical bullets are fired towards point P2 in the direction of the train's velocity with the same speed u , and they simultaneously reach point P2. Refer to Figure 4. Observer A measures the speed of the bullets on the ground, while observer B measures the speed of the bullets inside the train carriage. They both obtain the same numerical value, indicating that the speed of the bullets in their respective inertial reference frames is equal to u .

Figure 4: Bullet's Time

Observer A calculated that the bullet on the ground takes time T to reach P2. Based on the information provided by Observer B, the speed of the bullet inside the train relative to the train is u . Therefore, observer A calculated that the time required for the bullet inside the train to reach

P2 is:

$$T_1 = uT / (v + u). \quad (30)$$

Based on the information provided by Observer A, Observer B also knows that the bullet inside the train travels a distance of $uT - vT$ relative to the carriage. Therefore, Observer B also calculates that the time required for the bullet inside the train to reach P2 is

$$T_2 = (uT - vT) / u, \quad (31)$$

thus, we obtain:

$$T_2 = (u^2 - v^2) / u^2 * T_1. \quad (32)$$

As we can see, equation (32) is identical in form to equation (19). Therefore, based on equation (28), we can directly write the following expression:

$$T_2' = \sqrt{(u^2 - v^2) / u^2} * T_1. \quad (33)$$

Similarly, the bullet example is applicable to Lorentz transformations. We can use Lorentz transformations to calculate the time T' for the bullet inside the train carriage, and then use special relativity to calculate the time T_2' for the bullet inside the train carriage. We can then compare T' and T_2' and if our analysis is correct, T' and T_2' should yield the same numerical value. Let's now substitute specific values.

Assuming $u = 50$ m/s, $v = 30$ m/s, and $T = 100$ s, using equation (30), we obtain:

$$T_1 = 50 * 100 / (50 + 30) = 62.5. \quad (34)$$

Using equation (33), we obtain:

$$T_2' = \sqrt{(50^2 - 30^2) / 50^2} * T_1 = 0.8 * T_1 = 50. \quad (35)$$

The time calculated by Observer B inside the train as 40 s is actually equivalent to the time calculated by Observer A outside the train as 62.5 s. Although their numerical values appear different, they are actually the same time.

We can also apply the "bullet" example to Lorentz transformations, and using equation (11), we obtain:

$$T' = \gamma(T - v u T / u^2), \quad (36)$$

substituting $u = 50$ m/s, $v = 30$ m/s, and $T = 100$ s, we obtain:

$$T' = 5 / 4 * (100 - 30 * 50 * 100 / 50^2) = 50. \quad (37)$$

As we can see, the results obtained through Lorentz transformations are consistent with those obtained through special relativity. We can continue to substitute other data, as shown in the table 1 below:

u, v, T	T' (by Lorentz transformation)	T2' (by special relativity)
u=50 m/s, v=30 m/s, T=100 s	50 s'	50 s'
u=50 m/s, v=40 m/s, T=100 s	33.33 s'	33.33 s'
u=17m/s, v=8 m/s, T=100 s	60 s'	60 s'
u=13 m/s, v=5 m/s, T=100 s	66.67 s'	66.67 s'

Table 1: Time in S' Frame (s' denotes seconds in the S' frame)

As we can see, the time T2' calculated using the time formula in special relativity and the time T' calculated using the Lorentz transformations are consistent. Although these two equations have different mathematical forms, in terms of mathematical form, special relativity establishes the relationship between T2' and T1, while the Lorentz transformations establish the relationship between T' and T. Both T2' and T' refer to the time in the S' frame's time scale.

It may seem that the constancy of bullet speed in an inertial reference frame can also lead to the derivation of special relativity. However, we know that the constancy of the speed of light is the most important assumption of special relativity, and it introduces the concept of time dilation. So, does time really dilate?

According to our previous analysis, the reason for the different numerical values of time in different reference frames is due to their respective time and distance scales. In reality, their times are completely equal. However, if this adjustment of time and distance scales is not consciously made by us, then time dilation is real. On the other hand, the Lorentz transformations and special relativity are merely mathematical transformations of spacetime coordinates, and time does not actually dilate.

The Michelson-Morley experiment (MMX) triggered this physical controversy, and it is also through MMX that this controversy needs to be resolved.

5. Explanation of MMX

The results of MMX negated the theory of an absolute stationary ether and partially dragged ether. Only in the case where the ether is completely dragged by the Earth can MMX be reasonably explained. The phenomenon of stellar aberration is considered a rejection of the theory of completely dragged ether. However, if one truly understands the 19th-century research surrounding the ether, it can be discovered that answers had already been provided at that time. The experiments conducted by Michelson and Morley directly refuted Bradley and Young's explanation of stellar aberration [6][7]. A detailed analysis is provided here[8].

If it had been realized at that time that the density of the ether around the Earth might be

non-uniform and that the distribution of the ether might align with the distribution of the gravitational field, it could have been understood that light would undergo refraction in an inhomogeneous ether. In such a scenario, the fate of the theory of completely dragged ether might have been different. We cannot determine whether the propagation of light requires an ether; perhaps only the following assumption is necessary: on the Earth's surface, light is completely "dragged" by the gravitational field, which can explain MMX effectively. Of course, it is also possible that an ether truly exists, being captured by the Earth's gravitational field and exhibiting a non-uniform distribution similar to the gravitational field, while moving along with the Earth.

Figure 5: Light bending towards the gravitational source in an inhomogeneous ether or gravitational field.

If you insist that time in the moving frame S' slows down, you will fall into a self-contradictory dilemma. If we consider S as stationary and S' as moving, we can conclude that time in S' becomes slower. Likewise, if we consider S' as stationary and S as moving, we can also conclude that time in S becomes slower. This seems highly contradictory. However, if you understand one thing: this is simply a result of the different scales of time and distance in each inertial reference frame, then you won't truly believe that time is slowing down. The game of time dilation should come to an end.

6. Conclusion

The Lorentz transformations describe the differences in time calculations for the same event in different reference frames. On the other hand, special relativity describes the differences in time calculations for the same event within the same reference frame as observed by observers in different reference frames. Therefore, they have differences in their mathematical forms, but the

final calculation results are consistent. They both reveal a mathematical logic: the differences in time and distance scales between inertial reference frames result in different numerical values for time and distance calculations. We can use the Lorentz transformations or special relativity to perform transformations of spacetime coordinates between different reference frames.

We must be clear that the Lorentz transformations or special relativity are merely mathematical transformations, not physics itself. We can convert spacetime coordinates just like converting dollars to euros, but they are equivalent. We shouldn't feel that our wealth surpasses Elon Musk just because we have 100 billion Zimbabwean dollars. We shouldn't only focus on numbers and overlook the scales behind them. Nevertheless, we must express gratitude to great scientists like Michelson, Morley, Lorentz, Einstein, and others who have made outstanding contributions to exploring the unknown and advancing the natural sciences. However, we must also stand on the shoulders of giants to continue exploring, improving, and discovering what humanity already knows, as well as actively exploring the unknown.

If you are truly passionate about the physical sciences, read it and share your thoughts with us. We welcome skepticism and questions regarding this paper. We love science, and we love discussing and sharing knowledge.

I am Tony. Thank you for reading. I appreciate your time. If you have any further questions, feel free to ask.

7. Disclosures section

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest that could be perceived as influencing the objectivity and integrity of the research.

Ethical Approval: This study adheres to relevant ethical guidelines.

Informed Consent: Written informed consent has been obtained from all participants involved in this study.

Data Availability: The data and materials supporting the findings of this study can be made available upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

We affirm that the above disclosures accurately reflect the financial and non-financial relationships or interests that could be perceived as potentially influencing the research and its

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